

Data used for modeling in "A Systems Approach to Enhancing Resilience in the Water-Energy-Food Nexus: Incorporating Circular Economy Principles"

In this dataset, the data used for modeling technologies in a water-energy-food nexus model in Khark Island, an industrial island in Iran, are presented along with the main sources for their collection. The general data represent the average of the available data from the cited references.

Table 1. Residential electricity and water demand and municipal waste of Khark Island from 2019 to 2050 (1)

Year	Annual residential electricity demand (GWh)*	Annual residential water demand (1000 m ³)	Municipal waste (Ton)
2019	54.5	760	2844.2
2020	55.7	769.8	2871.8
2021	57.0	779.7	2897.6
2022	58.2	789.5	2921.8
2023	59.5	799.4	2944.3
2024	60.7	809.2	2965.8
2025	62.0	819.0	2985.6
2026	63.2	828.9	3004.4
2027	64.5	838.7	3021.9
2028	65.7	848.6	3038.0
2029	67.0	858.4	3053.4
2030	68.2	868.2	3067.5
2031	69.5	878.1	3081.0
2032	70.7	887.9	3093.4
2033	72.0	897.8	3105.1
2034	73.2	907.6	3115.9
2035	74.5	917.4	3126.0
2036	75.7	927.3	3135.4
2037	77.0	937.1	3144.1
2038	78.2	947.0	3152.5
2039	79.5	956.8	3160.2
2040	80.7	966.6	3167.3
2041	82.0	976.5	3174.0
2042	83.3	986.3	3180.0
2043	84.5	996.2	3185.7
2044	85.8	1006.0	3191.4
2045	87.0	1015.8	3196.1
2046	88.3	1025.7	3200.8
2047	89.5	1035.5	3205.2
2048	90.8	1045.4	3209.2
2049	92.0	1055.2	3213.3
2050	93.3	1065.0	3216.6

* The electricity demand in each cold month (from December to February) is 0.78 percent of the total demand and in each hot month (from March to November) is 10.85 percent of the annual demand. The increase in demand and waste production is due to the population growth.

** The increase in consumption is mainly based on population growth and climate condition assumptions.

Table 2. Costs of technologies modeled in this study

Technology	Capital cost	Fixed operational cost	Variable operational cost*	References
Carbon capture unit (absorption)	110 (\$/Ton/yr)	3 (\$/Ton/yr)	2 (\$/Ton)	(2–11)
Carbon capture unit (membrane)	350 (\$/Ton/yr)	20 (\$/Ton/yr)	-	
Direct air capture (DAC) - Solid sorbent	1000 (\$/Ton/y)	25 (\$/Ton/y)	10 (\$/Ton)	(12–14)
Direct air capture (DAC) - Liquid sorbent	830 (\$/Ton/y)	25 (\$/Ton/y)	3 (\$/Ton)	
Compressor (for CO ₂ transmission)	0.88 (\$/kg/s)	0.04 (\$/kg/s)	-	(10,15,16)
Compressor (for CO ₂ injection)	7.62 (\$/kg/s)	0.4 (\$/kg/s)	-	
Compressor (for natural gas injection)	24 (\$/m ³ /s)	1.2 (\$/m ³ /s)	-	
Water desalination (MED)	3.8 (\$/m ³ /yr)	0.05 (\$/m ³ /yr)	-	(17–19)
Water desalination (RO)	4 (\$/m ³ /yr)	0.19 (\$/m ³ /yr)	0.12 (\$/m ³)	
Atmospheric water generator (AWG)	329 (\$/m ³ /y)	26 (\$/m ³ /y)	56 (\$/m ³)	(20–24)
Boiler	230 (\$/kW)	6.7 (\$/kW)	-	(25,26)
Greenhouse (cucumber)	157.1 (\$/m ²)	1.95 (\$/m ²)	-	(27–31)
Hydroponic greenhouse (cucumber)	261.9 (\$/m ²)	2.94 (\$/m ²)	-	
Greenhouse (eggplant)	157.1 (\$/m ²)	3 (\$/m ²)	-	
Hydroponic greenhouse (eggplant)	261.9 (\$/m ²)	4.5 (\$/m ²)	-	
Greenhouse (tomato)	157.1 (\$/m ²)	2.1 (\$/m ²)	-	
Hydroponic greenhouse (tomato)	261.9 (\$/m ²)	3.3 (\$/m ²)	-	
Date cultivation (ring basin irrigation)	0.74 (\$/m ²)	0.82 (\$/m ²)	0.001 (\$/m ²)	
Date cultivation (drip irrigation)	0.78 (\$/m ²)	0.66 (\$/m ²)	0.001 (\$/m ²)	

Technology	Capital cost	Fixed operational cost	Variable operational cost*	References	
Landfill	110 (\$/Ton/y)	4.5 (\$/Ton/y)	-	(38,39)	
Anaerobic digestion biomethane production	4.5 (\$/m ³ /y)	0.3 (\$/m ³ /y)	-	(40,41)	
Anaerobic digestion power plant (CHP)	4900 (\$/kW)	201 (\$/kW)	-	(42–47)	
Waste incineration power plant (CHP)	6300 (\$/kW)	189 (\$/kW)	-		
Gasification power plant (CHP)	5900 (\$/kW)	265 (\$/kW)	-	(48–50)	
Existing natural gas power plant (gas turbine)	-	13 (\$/kW)	-	(51–58)	
Natural gas power plant (gas turbine)	805 (\$/kW)	13 (\$/kW)	-		
Natural gas power plant (steam turbine, wet cooling)	828 (\$/kW)	18 (\$/kW)	-		
Natural gas power plant (steam turbine, once-through cooling)	816.2 (\$/kW)	18 (\$/kW)	-		
Natural gas power plant (steam turbine, dry cooling)	927.4 (\$/kW)	18 (\$/kW)	-		
Natural gas power plant (combined cycle, wet cooling)	963 (\$/kW)	15.4 (\$/kW)	-		
Natural gas power plant (combined cycle, once-through cooling)	949.2 (\$/kW)	15.4 (\$/kW)	-		
Natural gas power plant (combined cycle, dry cooling)	1078.5 (\$/kW)	15.4 (\$/kW)	-		
Natural gas power plant (gas microturbine; CHP)	2480.8 (\$/kW)	12.4 (\$/kW)	-		(59–65)
Natural gas power plant (gas engine; CHP)	2215 (\$/kW)	31 (\$/kW)	-		
Solar power plant (floating PV)**	1440 (\$/kW)	10.6 (\$/kW)	0.085 (\$/GJ)	(66,67)	

Technology	Capital cost	Fixed operational cost	Variable operational cost*	References
Solar power plant (onshore PV)**	1200 (\$/kW)	5.3 (\$/kW)	-	(68–72)
CSP power plant (for heat)**	675 (\$/kW _{th})***	13.5 (\$/kW _{th})***	-	(73–77)
Wind power plant**	1530 (\$/kW)	0.37 (\$/kW)	-	(78–80)
Water injection pump	0.05 (\$/m ³ /s)	0.003 (\$/m ³ /s)	-	(81–83)
Wastewater treatment (RO+UF)	3.31 (\$/m ³ /yr)	0.03 (\$/m ³ /yr)	0.02 (\$/m ³)	(84–88)
Caustic plant	870 (\$/Ton/y)	30 (\$/Ton/y)	-	(89)
Ammonia/urea production (using natural gas)	1700 (\$/Ton/y)	50 (\$/Ton/y)	-	(90–94)
Ammonia/urea production (using water+CO ₂)	2600 (\$/Ton/y)	80 (\$/Ton/y)	-	
Methanol production (using natural gas)	720 (\$/Ton/y)	25 (\$/Ton/y)	-	(95–104)
Methanol production (using water+CO ₂)	1800 (\$/Ton/y)	60 (\$/Ton/y)	-	
Methanol production (using biomass)	1860 (\$/Ton/y)	74 (\$/Ton/y)	-	(102,105,106)
NGL recovery plant	0.38 (\$/m ³ /y)	0.013 (\$/m ³ /y)	-	(107–109)
Flaring technology	0.15 (\$/m ³ /y)	0.03 (\$/m ³ /y)	-	(110)

* The cost of purchasing inputs like electricity that are produced in the project is excluded from the variable cost. However, the cost of buying water, electricity, natural gas for energy sector use, and natural gas for industrial sector use from the grid is considered to be about 0.16 \$/m³, 0.7 \$/GWh, 0.0012 \$/m³, and 0.023 \$/m³ respectively (111–113).

** In this research, it is assumed that the capital cost of solar and wind technologies will decrease annually by approximately 1.5% and 0.5% respectively, reflecting their advancements.

*** kW_{th} is related to thermal energy production and kW is related to electricity energy production.

Table 3. The ratio of inputs and outputs of atmospheric water generator (AWG), water treatment and desalination technologies to the clean output water

Technology	Input				Output	References
	Sea water, wastewater, or humidity (m ³ /m ³)	Heat (GJ/m ³)	Land (m ² /m ³)	Electricity (GJ/m ³)	Brine (m ³ /m ³)	
MED	4.5	0.21	0.002	0.007	3.5	

Technology	Input				Output	References
	Sea water, wastewater, or humidity (m ³ /m ³)	Heat (GJ/m ³)	Land (m ² /m ³)	Electricity (GJ/m ³)	Brine (m ³ /m ³)	
RO	2.4	-	0.001	0.014	1.4	(17,84,86,114–122)
RO + UF	1.2	-	0.001	0.003	0.2	
AWG	1.43	-	-	6.84	-	(21,123–126)

Table 4. The ratio of inputs of date cultivation to the cultivation land

Technology	Water (m ³ /m ²)	Electricity (GJ/m ²)	Precipitation (m ³ /m ²)	References
Date cultivation (ring basin irrigation)	3.57	0.0003	0.26	(35,36,127–132)
Date cultivation (drip irrigation)	1.88	0.0005	0.26	

Table 5. The ratio of outputs of date cultivation to the cultivation land

Technology	Date (kg/m ²)	Fruit waste (kg/m ²)	Palm waste (kg/m ²)	Evapotranspiration (m ³ /m ²)	Surface water (m ³ /m ²)	Ground water (m ³ /m ²)	References
Date cultivation (ring basin irrigation)	0.648	0.087	0.3	3.6	0.18	0.05	(33,131–140)
Date cultivation (drip irrigation)	0.794	0.106	0.3	2.012	0.102	0.026	

Table 6. The ratio of inputs and outputs of Onshore lands (except date cultivation lands) to the related land

Technology	Input	Output			References
	Precipitation (m ³ /m ²)	Evapotranspiration (m ³ /m ²)	Surface water (m ³ /m ²)	Ground water (m ³ /m ²)	
Onshore lands (Except date cultivation lands)	0.26	0.19	0.05	0.02	(129,130,132,141)

Table 7. The ratio of inputs and outputs of Offshore land (water body) to the related land

Technology	Input		Output		References
	Precipitation (m ³ /m ²)	Surface water (m ³ /m ²)	Evapotranspiration (m ³ /m ²)	Surface water (m ³ /m ²)	
Water body (Offshore land)	0.26	1.73	1.84	0.15	(129,130,142,143)

Table 8. The ratio of inputs and outputs of greenhouses to the area of cultivation land

Technology	Input			Output*		References
	Water (m ³ /m ²)	Electricity (GJ/m ²)	Heat (GJ/m ²)	Crop (kg/m ²)	Crop's waste (kg/m ²)	
Greenhouse (cucumber)	0.56	0.049	0.88	23.23	2.41	(140,144–155)
Hydroponic greenhouse (cucumber)	0.69	0.059	0.79	34.85	3.61	
Greenhouse (eggplant)	0.7	0.055	0.73	27.4	2.9	(147,152,155–161)
Hydroponic greenhouse (eggplant)	0.84	0.065	0.66	41.1	4.3	
Greenhouse (tomato)	0.72	0.043	0.81	25.72	5.53	(29,140,145,147,148,152,155,162–170)
Hydroponic greenhouse (tomato)	0.76	0.056	0.73	39.19	8.43	

* In the case of controlled injection of CO₂ in the greenhouse atmosphere, the crop yield would increase by at least 10 percent (171,172). The required amount of CO₂ injection for tomato, cucumber, and eggplant is 5, 6, and 5.5 kg/m² per hour, respectively (27).

Table 9. The ratio of inputs of fossil heat and or power generation technologies to the produced electricity

Technology	Water (m ³ /GJ)	Land (m ² /GJ)	Natural gas (m ³ /GJ)	References
Existing natural gas power plant (gas turbine)	-	0.013	184	(55,56,173–176)
Natural gas power plant (gas turbine)	-	0.064	71	
Natural gas power plant (steam turbine, wet cooling)	1.27	0.033	68	

Technology	Water (m³/GJ)	Land (m²/GJ)	Natural gas (m³/GJ)	References
Natural gas power plant (steam turbine, once-through cooling)	36.7	0.033	67.6	
Natural gas power plant (steam turbine, dry cooling)	0.002	0.033	68.3	
Natural gas power plant (combined cycle, wet cooling)	0.23	0.04	50	
Natural gas power plant (combined cycle, once- through cooling)	14.3	0.04	49.7	
Natural gas power plant (combined cycle, dry cooling)	0.002	0.04	50.2	
Natural gas power plant (gas microturbine; CHP)	-	0.044	107	(59,61,63,175,177– 179)
Natural gas power plant (gas engine; CHP)	-	0.044	79	
Boiler*	-	-	33	(180,181)

* The ratio for this technology is based on its heat production.

Table 10. The ratio of inputs of fossil heat and or power generation technologies to the produced electricity

Technology	Wastewater (m³/GJ)	CO₂ (kg/GJ)	Heat (GJ/GJ)	References
Existing natural gas power plant (gas turbine)	-	330.5	-	(182,183)
Natural gas power plant (gas turbine)	-	130.5	-	
Natural gas power plant (steam turbine, wet cooling)	0.3	119	-	
Natural gas power plant (steam turbine, once-through cooling)	36.5	118.4	-	
Natural gas power plant (steam turbine, dry cooling)	0	119.6	-	
Natural gas power plant (combined cycle, wet cooling)	0.002	108	-	
Natural gas power plant (combined cycle, once-through cooling)	14.3	107.5	-	
Natural gas power plant (combined cycle, dry cooling)	0	108.5	-	
Natural gas power plant (gas microturbine; CHP)	-	186	1.85	(63,65,177– 179)

Technology	Wastewater (m ³ /GJ)	CO ₂ (kg/GJ)	Heat (GJ/GJ)	References
Natural gas power plant (gas engine; CHP)	-	142	1.23	
Boiler*	-	65.4	1	(184–186)

* The ratio for this technology is based on its heat production.

Table 11. The ratio of inputs of renewable heat or power generation technologies to the produced heat or electricity

Technology	Water (m ³ /GJ)	Land (m ² /GJ)	Solar/wind energy (GJ/GJ)	References
Solar power plant (floating PV)*	0.02	0.72	5.75	(187,188)
Solar power plant (onshore PV)	0.02	0.89	6.45	(189–191)
CSP power plant (for heat)**	0.025	0.33	1.41	(192–196)
Wind power plant*	-	10.69	2.5	(197–199)

* This power plant leads to the reduction of evaporation and transpiration by about 31% in practical conditions and thus increases the available surface water (200–202).
** The ratio for this technology is based on its heat production.

Table 12. The ratio of inputs of bio-energy plants to the produced electricity

Technology	Water (m ³ /GJ)	Land (m ² /GJ)	Municipal waste (kg/GJ)	Agricultural waste (kg/GJ)	References
Anaerobic digestion power plant (CHP)*	0.3	0.63	1180	630	(46,203–222)
Waste incineration power plant (CHP)	0.9	0.14	700	700	
Gasification plant (CHP)	0.19	0.38	527.8	202.8	(50,223–225)

* Municipal and agricultural waste required for producing a unit of electricity are considered and calculated separately.

Table 13. The ratio of inputs of bio-energy plants to the produced electricity

Technology	Wastewater (m ³ /GJ)	CO ₂ (kg/GJ)	Heat (GJ/GJ)	References
Anaerobic digestion power plant (CHP)*	0.11	100	1.14	(203–207,210–212,226–230)
Waste incineration power plant (CHP)	0.33	620	1.79	

Technology	Wastewater (m ³ /GJ)	CO ₂ (kg/GJ)	Heat (GJ/GJ)	References
Gasification plant (CHP)	0.04	250	2.2	(49,223)

Table 14. The ratio of inputs and outputs of biomethane production to produced biomethane

Technology	Input				Output		References
	Water (m ³ /m ³)	Land (m ² /m ³)	Municipal waste (kg/m ³)	Agricultural waste (kg/m ³)	Wastewater (m ³ /m ³)	CO ₂ (kg/m ³)	
Anaerobic digestion biomethane production	0.004	0.009	16.7	8.8	0.0014	0.4	(44,208,209,227,230–233)

Table 15. The ratio of inputs and outputs of bio-methanol production to produced bio-methanol

Technology	Input					Output		References
	Water (m ³ /kg)	Electricity (GJ/kg)	Land (m ² /kg)	Municipal waste (kg/kg)	Agricultural waste (kg/kg)	Wastewater (m ³ /kg)	CO ₂ (kg/kg)	
Methanol production (using biomass)	0.0053	0.0047	0.0037	2.6	2.5	0.0029	1.8	(100,102,105,234–236)

Table 16. The ratio of inputs of methanol, ammonia/urea, and caustic production plants to the main product

Technology	Electricity (GJ/kg)	Water (m ³ /kg)	Land (m ² /kg)	Natural gas (m ³ /kg)	Heat (GJ/kg)	CO ₂ (kg/kg)	Brine water (m ³ /kg)	References
Caustic plant	0.008	0.07	0.0007	-	0.0006	-	0.02	(89,237–240)
Ammonia/urea production (using natural gas)	0.0006	0.0009	0.001	0.49	-	-	-	(91,93,94,241–244)
Ammonia/urea production (using water+CO ₂)	0.02	0.0009	0.001	-	-	0.73	-	
Methanol production (using natural gas)	0.001	0.09	0.00004	0.92	-	-	-	(95–100,102,104,244–246)
Methanol production (using water+CO ₂)	0.04	0.03	0.00004	-	-	1.44	-	

Table 17. The ratio of outputs of methanol, ammonia/urea, and caustic production plants to the main product

Technology	Wastewater (m ³ /kg)	CO ₂ (kg/kg)	Cl ₂ (kg/kg)	References
Caustic plant	0.02	-	0.88	(89,237,240,247)
Ammonia/urea production (using natural gas)	0.0005	0.3	-	(91,93,94,241,248)

Technology	Wastewater (m ³ /kg)	CO ₂ (kg/kg)	Cl ₂ (kg/kg)	References
Ammonia/urea production (using water+CO ₂)	0.0005	-	-	
Methanol production (using natural gas)	0.0006	0.49	-	(97–99,103,245,249)
Methanol production (using water+CO ₂)	0.00057	-	-	

Table 18. The ratio of inputs of the pump and compressor technologies to the outlet fluid

Technology	Inlet fluid	Electricity	References
Compressor (for CO ₂ transmission)	1 (kg/kg)	0.0005 (GJ/kg)	(3,4,9,81,82,250–258)
Compressor (for CO ₂ injection)	1 (kg/kg)	0.00006 (GJ/kg)	
Compressor (for natural gas injection)	9 (m ³ /m ³)	0.016 (GJ/m ³)	
Water injection pump	1(m ³ /m ³)	0.00001 (GJ/m ³)*	
* The electricity consumption for water injection is about 0.03 J/m ³ , but to consider a meaningful value in the modeling, the small value of 0.00001 GJ/m ³ has been used.			

Table 19. The ratio of inputs of oil field for oil extraction to the extracted oil

Oil extraction method	Injection fluid	Water (m ³ /toe)*	References
Water injection	2.74 (m ³ /toe)	0.035	(259–266)
Natural gas injection	477 (m ³ /toe)	0.035	
CO ₂ injection	3193 (kg/toe)	0.035	
* toe = ton oil equivalent			

Table 20. The ratio of outputs of the oil field to the extracted oil

Technology	Associated gas (m ³ /toe)	Wastewater (m ³ /toe)	References
Oil well	357.1	3.43	(257,260,267,268)
toe = ton oil equivalent The output of the oil field decreases over time. According to the life of the well, the annual decrease in oil and gas extraction is considered to be 4 percent; on the other hand, the annual water extraction increases by 1.5 percent (16,260,266,269).			

Table 21. The ratio of inputs and outputs of carbon capture technologies to the pure CO₂ output

Technology	Input					Output	References
	CO ₂ (kg/kg)	Amine solvent (m ³ /kg)	Water (m ³ /kg)	Electricity (GJ/kg)	Heat (GJ/kg)	Wastewater (m ³ /kg)	
Carbon capture unit (absorption)	1.11	0.000001	0.002	-	0.004	0.0001	(2,4,5,7,250,270–272)
Carbon capture unit (membrane)	1.11	-	-	0.0004	-	-	(9,15,271,273–275)
Direct air capture (DAC) - Solid sorbent	1.14	-	-	0.0014	0.005	-	(14,83,276–279)
Direct air capture (DAC) - Liquid sorbent	1.14	-	0.004	0.0014	0.0065	-	

Table 22. The ratio of inputs and outputs of associated gas management technologies to the managed associated gas

Technology	Input		Output				References
	Land (m ² /m ³)	Water (m ³ /m ³)	CO ₂ (kg/m ³)	CH ₄ (m ³ /m ³)	C ₂ H ₆ (m ³ /m ³)	C ₃ H ₄ and C ₃₊ (m ³ /m ³)	
NGL recovery plant	0.0001	0.0003	0.04	0.71	0.05	0.11	(107,109,280–285)
Flaring technology	-	-	2.2	-	-	-	(286–288)

Table 23. Capacity factor, availability factor, and lifetime of technologies

Technology	Capacity factor (%)	Availability factor (%)	Lifetime (year)	References
Carbon capture unit (absorption)	100	85	37	(5,289–292)

Technology	Capacity factor (%)	Availability factor (%)	Lifetime (year)	References
Carbon capture unit (membrane)	100	92	25	(9,271,273,292,293)
Direct air capture (DAC)	100	90	20	(276,279)
Compressor	100	96	12.5	(289,294)
Water desalination (MED)	100	88	25	(295)
Water desalination (RO)	100	92	20	(19,296,297)
Atmospheric water generator (AWG)	100	90	15	(20,298)
Boiler	81	85	15	(299)
Greenhouse	100	100	15	(300,301)
Date cultivation	100	100	70	(135,302)
Oil well	100	100	33	(251,303)
Anaerobic digestion biomethane production	100	85	20	(227,304,305)
Anaerobic digestion power plant (CHP)	100	85	20	(43,47,227,306,307)
Waste incineration power plant (CHP)	100	85	25	
Gasification power plant (CHP)	100	85	22	(47,48)
Natural gas power plant (gas turbine)	81	92	20	(308–310)
Natural gas power plant (steam turbine)	94	94	45	
Natural gas power plant (combined cycle)	81	91	20	
Natural gas power plant (gas microturbine; CHP)	81	96	10	(61,269,310–315)
Natural gas power plant (gas engine; CHP)	81	95	20	
Solar power plant	Table 24	94	20	(68,316–320)
Wind power plant	Table 24	97	20	(321,322)
Pump	100	91	19	(323,324)
Wastewater treatment (RO+UF)	100	93	20	(118,325,326)
Caustic plant	100	92	25	(89)

Technology	Capacity factor (%)	Availability factor (%)	Lifetime (year)	References
Ammonia/urea production (using natural gas)	100	92	25	(90,91,241,327,328)
Ammonia/urea production (using water+CO2)	100	92	25	
Methanol production (using natural gas)	100	92	25	(95,98,99,102,104,329,330)
Methanol production (using water+CO2)	100	92	25	
Methanol production (using biomass)	100	85	20	(102,105,330)
NGL recovery plant	100	92	35	(331,332)

Table 24. The capacity factor of wind and solar power plants in Khark Island (333)

Month	Solar power plant capacity factor (%)	Wind power plant capacity factor (%)	Month	Solar power plant capacity factor (%)	Wind power plant capacity factor (%)
January	14.5	41.6	July	20.8	44.1
February	18.2	30	August	21.2	23.7
March	21.5	29.6	September	22	27.1
April	20.5	29.8	October	17.9	10.6
May	20.9	19.8	November	18.5	15.2
June	21.4	36.7	December	16.7	20

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